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THE PROCESS OF ENANTIOSEMY IN NIZAMI GANJAVI AND GATRAN TABRIZI'S CREATIVE WORKS

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ЭНАНТИОСЕМИЯ В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ НИЗАМИ ГЯНДЖЕВИ И ГАТРАНА ТЕБРИЗИ

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Abstract. The article deals with “enantiosemy” the term which shows situation that carry two meanings, the first it’s meaning is “exist”, in second is “not exist”. It has opposite meanings. This process happens in vocabulary. The history of this process is connected with the ancient history of language.

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Аннотация. Энантисемиа — это термин, который используется для слов, выраженных в ситуации двойного смысла. Например, словосочетание «слушать лекцию» можно понять как «восприятие» (понимание) и как «услышать». Энантисемиа (греч. *εναντιο* — противоположный, *σημία* — значение) означает развитие антонимического смысла и поляризацию смысла слова.

Слова, созданные в процессе энантисемии, принадлежат к одинаковому звуковому комплексу, а для представления различных значений ближе становятся к омонимам. Но в отличие от омонимов, они означают противоположные значения. В связи с этим они по значению приближаются к антонимам. Но антонимы относятся к разным звуковым комплексам и разному фонетическому составу и обозначают противоположные слова, а слова в энантисемии принадлежат к одинаковому фонетическому составу, но являются противоположными словами.

Keywords: enantiosemy, opposite, meaning, vocabulary, exist, not exist, language, connected, ancient history process.

Ключевые слова: энантисемиа, отражение смысл, одинаковый смысл, процесса связано, словарной состав, история процесса.

“Enantiosemy” is a term used to express the situation that a word has two meanings. E.g. In the phrase “listen to a lecture”, you can understand the verb “listen” as “comprehend”, also as “conform and hear”. What is Enantiosemy?

Enantiosemy – (Greek word *enantios-* *enantios-* opposite + *sema-* sign) means the development of antonym meanings, polarise of meanings.

Words formed with the enantiosemy have the same sound complex, are close to homonyms due to the the different meanings. But, in contrast to homonyms, here means opposite meanings to each other. Words formed with the enantiosemy are close to antonyms due to the the opposite meanings. Although the antonyms are opposite meaningful words having different sound complex

and phonetic structure but they (enantiosemy) are the same phonetic structural, opposite meaningful words [3, p. 176].

Azerbaijani language is one of the developed and rich languages of the world. All words in our language constitute the vocabulary of Azerbaijani language. It is not so easy to know the meaning of all words in the vocabulary of our language. But there is such a lexical sphere that, every Azerbaijanian always and everywhere knows the meaning of the words included there. Words included this sphere constitute the basic vocabulary fund of our language [1, p. 56].

The lexicology of Azerbaijani language studies the modern condition of the vocabulary formed related to the history of nation who speaks this language [6, p. 10]. One of the interesting word groups in the vocabulary is to express the opposite meaning each other which the words have the same sound complex. Such words form the enantiosemy case.

Enantiosemy case in Azerbaijani language is available as an interesting language case.

But this case escaped notice up to date, has not been studied in Azerbaijan linguistics. As we noted, enantiosemy express the opposite meanings of the word having the same sound complex.

Enantiosemy case is a process taking place in the vocabulary of the language. The history of this process is related to the ancient times [4, p. 59].

The coverage of the enantiosemy on parts of speech is broad. This case evinces in different parts of speech.

Enantiosemy in parts of speech, in Azerbaijani language.

1. Enantiosemy in Nouns

A noun is one of the richest one among the parts of speech. The Noun is rich either in lexical-semantic or grammatical aspect. One of the cases enriching nouns in lexical-semantic aspect is enantiosemy.

2. Enantiosemy in Adjectives

Adjective differs from the other parts of speech in terms of lexical group of meaning. The case enriching the group of meaning is enantiosemy.

3. Enantiosemy in Numerals

Types of meaning of numerals are not available in other parts of speech. Enantiosemy is a case that enriching the types of meaning of the numerals.

4. Enantiosemy in Verbs

Verbs differ from the other parts of speech with their national identity. Semantic issues are rich in verbs. The semantic richness in verbs is also formed by enantiosemy.

5. Enantiosemy in Adverbs. Adverbs are formed as a main parts of speech later. Therefore, relation of other parts of speech with adverbs is natural case. Also the process of enantiosemy is a natural process.

6. Enantiosemy in other parts of speech.

When we say other parts of speech we mean auxiliary parts of speech. Auxiliary parts of speech have no lexical meaning, therefore enantiosemy is weak in them.

Stylistic possibilities of enantiosemy in Azerbaijani language

1. Service for the effectiveness of speech

Enantiosemy has informative feature when it becomes as a special element of the form of speech, especially art language. Speech environment that is used attracts the attention with its effectiveness. Intensive refer to them in artistic texts increase the aesthetic essence of the text.

2. Service for the fluency of speech

Enantiosemy has important role in the fluency of speech. They get out the neutrality either in spoken language or the language of artistic works in terms of stylistic. It has special importance in the fluency of speech and the text, intonation view.

3. Service for the figurativeness of speech

Enantiosemy has very rich stylistic qualities. They have crucial role in the forming of figurativeness. According to these features, they easily find a way either in everyday and communication language or in artistic creativity.

4. Service for the clarity of speech

Enantiosemy is easily adapted to the content of artistic texts due to its stylistic clarity. Service for clarity of speech brings special freshness to the way of saying. They serve to the purpose of creating internal communication between ideas are directed to a clear testimony of essence.

5. The role of the artistic arrangement of artistic speech

Enantiosemy has rich stylistic qualities. Therefore, this easily takes place in speech. It distinguished by its activity in perfect shaping of the speech structure.

6. Service for satira, humour, comicality .

One of the main advantages of enantiosemy is the service in formation of satirical content, the creation of gentle humour and comic element. Opportunities of expressiveness are widely used either in speech or literary-artistic texts. The content of speech in them has special way of originality.

7. The role in the formation of quibble (opposite meaning)

Enantiosemy has great importance in creativity of quibble, pun. This style is widely used in artistic works, specially in dramatic works and dialogues of epic works. They have colorful stylistic feature.

8. The role in formation of antithesis etc.

The presence of enantiosemy is one of the means of perception and use with discrepancies. In the expression of the meaning, enantiosemy has important role as antonyms in comparing of concepts standing on opposite part. As a perfect means of expression, enantiosemy also are very active in the creativity of artistic contrast.

Enantiosemy can be found in Azerbaijani literature classics. Enantiosemy are enough in the creativity of our genius writers Nizami Ganjavi, Gatran Tabrizli, Muhammad Fuzuli, Imamaddin Nasimi, and other classics.

Genius Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi was born in 1141, Ganja, he lived all his life in this city and was buried in this city in 1209. Nizami is the author of "Quinary" consists of five masnavi (long narrative poems) ("The Storehouse of Mysteries", "Leyli and Majnun", "Khosrov və Shirin", "Seven Beauties", "Iskandarnamə"), lyrical ghazals and other works [2, p. 356].

When we pay attention to classic ghazals of Nizami Ganjavi, the enantiosemy can be found in those works.

Afərin hüsnünə, mən bir belə dilbər istərəm ,

Gecələr şəm yanar, sən kimi gövhər istərəm! [5, p. 21]

Translation in English:

A beautiful view, the most beautiful girl I want.

Light in night as you, natural beautiful girl I want! [5, p. 21]

Here, the word "Well done!" was used in the meaning of "good".

For example: Well done! How evil you did!

In this sentence the word "Well done!" is in "bad" irony, open meaning. Let's pay attention to the other ghazals of Nizami Ganjavi.

Öz yaman halımı açdım sənə .diqqət verəsən

O qara gözlərinə azca nəsihət verəsən. [5, p. 66]

Translation in English:

I talk to you mw bad mood, take care of me.

Give some attention to your black eyes, not to burn lovers. [5, p. 66]

Here the poet gave the "evil" in the meaning of "bad".

Nizami skillfully used from quatrain genre in order to express lyrical feelings with different contents. We saw him as powerful humanist of West renaissance. [5, p. 10]

We can meet “enantiosemy” process in Nizami’s quatrains.

Qəlbim qoya,eyləsəm şikayət səndən ,
Gör ki,nə deyər könül nəhayət səndən.
Sirr açmaq əgər olmasa bu,barədə,
Eylərdim axır yaman hekayət səndən [5, p. 154]

Translation in English:

I deeply tasted wonderful taste of wine of love
And saw deeply many bad and good things.
What to say, I oppressed from sweet life.
Don’t ask me what I saw deeply! [5, p. 154]

Here the word “evil” is enantiosemy but in “a bad” meaning.

Eşqin meyini daddım əyan dərdindən.
Gördüm nə qədər yaxşı –yaman dərdindən.
Bezdim.nə deyim qəminlə şirin candan .
Gəl sorma nələr gördüm. aman. dərdindən! [5, p. 151]

Translation in English:

If my heart let me I complain about you.
See what is desire says about you.
If we cant open secret about it.
I wolud say a bad story about you. [5, p. 154]

Here the word “evil” is enantiosemy but in “a good” meaning.

This writings let us to speak about poets’s sense and savings. [5, p. 10]

One of the well known poet of classic poetry is Gatran Mansur son Tabrizi. He was born in 1012 in farmer family. He learn deeply classic poetry and began to write poets from 15-16 years old.

When he was 20 years old he travelled to Ganja and was adimisioned to Sahddadilar palace. When he was there he wrote wonderfl works about Azerbaijan nature.

His odes come to our period. He is the author of “Oguzname” poem and “Ettesafir ” explanatory dictionary.

He died in 1088 and burned in Ganja. We can meet enantiosemyin his works. (2,46) For example:

Dünyanın həşmətli şahı canlılarçındır günəş,
Yox elə bir fikri ki, məclis, döyüş meydan deyil! [2, p. 55]

Translation in English:

The world high level king, is sun for human.
There is no thought about that assembly is not battle square!
[2, p. 55]

Here the word “not” means “exist”. For example:

Gül dərərik bir gülüstandan keşikçi var ikən,
Yox keşikçi, indi gül dərmək bizə asan deyil. [2, p. 54]

Translation in English:

We pick flowers if there is guard.
If there is not guard, it is difficult to pick flowers. [2, p. 54]

Here the word “not” means “not exist”.

Then, enantiosemy is a term for words which carry two meanings. In the first it's meaning is "exist", in second is "not exist".

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